

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

EFFECTS OF TILLAGE, IRRIGATION METHODS, AND FERTILIZER NORMS ON THE STRUCTURAL INDICATORS OF THE SOYBEAN VARIETY SEGALIA

Safiev E.

Ph.D. Candidate

Seyidaliyev N.

*Doctor of Agricultural Sciences; Professor
Azerbaijan State Agrarian University*

Abstract

This study explores the effects of various tillage depths, irrigation methods, and fertilizer application rates on the structural indicators of the soybean variety Segalia. Conducted in the Ganja-Gazakh region of Azerbaijan, the research highlights how different agrotechnical approaches impact yield, protein, and oil content, as well as the mass of 1000 seeds. The findings indicate that soybeans irrigated using drip systems and fertilized at a rate of N100P80K50 kg/ha demonstrated the most significant improvements in all measured indicators, with a yield increase of 5-8 centners/ha, protein content boost by 3-5%, oil content enhancement by 4-6%, and an increase in seed weight by 5-10 grams. These results underscore the potential of optimized irrigation and fertilization practices to enhance soybean productivity and nutritional quality, which is vital for advancing sustainable agriculture in Azerbaijan.

Keywords: cultivation, soybean, grain yield, protein, oil, 1000 seeds, fertilization, irrigation.

In the "State Program on the Socio-Economic Development of the Regions of the Republic of Azerbaijan in 2019–2023" it is noted that the development of the regions of the Republic of Azerbaijan is an important part of the successfully implemented sustainable socio-economic development strategy in the country. The implementation of tasks envisaged in state programs accepted and successfully implemented in the field of regional development, as well as in orders on additional measures for the socio-economic development of the regions, creates conditions for the sustainable development of the non-oil sector in the country, the improvement of the quality of communal services and social infrastructure provision in the regions, the further improvement of the business environment, the increase of investments, the opening of new enterprises, jobs, and consequently, the increase of employment of the population.

The instructions given by the President of Azerbaijan Ilham Aliyev on the development of traditional fields in agriculture are being successfully implemented.

Soybean is an important oil-protein plant with a very wide application field. Currently, up to 1000 food products, including oil, yogurt, milk, cheese, etc., are made from soybeans. Products obtained from soybeans are quickly digested by the human body. When soybean protein is added to protein obtained from other plants, its nutritional value increases even more. Products obtained from soybeans are an excellent diet for diabetic patients, people suffering from obesity, and vegetarians. They are very important in the treatment of cardiovascular and cancer diseases in humans and in regulating cholesterol in the blood.

In the Ganja-Dashkasan economic regions, studies conducted by A.P.Khudiev and Q.Y.Mammadov have investigated the feed value and quality indicators of clean and mixed crops of soybeans and corn under irrigation conditions. It was determined that 5418 kg of

feed units and 903 kg of digestible protein were obtained from soybean grown in pure crops.

Studies conducted by Sh.H.Ahmadov, M.Y.Rzaev, and Z.M.Abdullayeva at the Research Institute of Crop Production in Absheron conditions have examined the effect of irrigation methods and fertilizer norms on the yield of soybeans grown in fallow land. There are extensive opportunities for growing soybeans in Azerbaijan and obtaining high grain and green mass yields from them. Soybean is a heat-loving plant, and the total temperature required for its development and maturation is 1700-32000 C. The optimal temperature for seed germination should be 20-220 C. During the flowering and pod formation period, soybean has a high demand for heat. Besides spring crops, growing soybeans in fallow land after barley harvesting is also economically very beneficial. Sowing in fallow land on irrigated soils makes it possible to obtain additional grain and feed products from a unit area and to use reclamation objects efficiently. In this case, the soil is enriched with organic matter, salinization is prevented, wind erosion and weed control issues are completely resolved. Cultivation of crops in fallow land in large farm enterprises increases the efficiency of using labor force, irrigation water, irrigation networks, agricultural machinery, and equipment.

Global ecological processes occurring in nature require the development of new tillage technologies and fertilization systems that save energy carriers for different agro-ecological regions and crops in our country. In modern times, one of the important issues facing agricultural science is the increase in the productivity of grain-legume crops.

Soybean is one of the important crops widely spread in world agriculture. Due to its multi-purpose use, it is superior to other agricultural crops from an agronomic and ecological point of view. During the vegetation period, a total of 1700-32000 C active temperature is required for the formation of a high yield. Under

optimal air temperature conditions, the biological activity, viability, and productivity of the plant increase. A decrease in temperature reduces the chemical processes occurring in the plant, biological activity, viability, and productivity.

One of the main measures to increase production in the grain and feed sector in our country is to increase the productivity and quality of grain and feed crops grown in fallow land. The analysis of the results obtained from scientific research and advanced farms shows that it is possible to obtain a crop twice a year from a unit land area under irrigation conditions in the lowland and foothill regions of our country. Corn, sorghum, barley, beet, sunflower, soybean, green peas, and other feed crops grown in fallow land provide a high amount of quality feed products.

The deficiency of food protein is observed in many countries of the world. The protein deficiency in countries is compensated by livestock products. To solve this problem, it is more appropriate to grow high-protein crops. One of these crops is soybean, which is both a technical and feed crop. Being rich in unique irreplaceable vitamins, it is considered a valuable raw material in food production.

Soybean is a highly profitable crop in the agrarian sector, with significant economic, ecological, and social importance. Among leguminous crops in the world, soybean ranks first in oil production. With a planting area of 120 million ha, 60% of the produced plant oil comes from soybean, and soybean production was 320 million tons in 2015. In the Krasnodar region of Russia, the grain yield of soybean is 2.0 t/ha, making it economically profitable.

Russia ranks 11th in the world for soybean production. Therefore, the country is forced to import soybean seeds. According to the Russian Statistics Committee, the soybean planting area was 2,919 thousand ha in 2018 and increased to 2,382 thousand ha in 2019.

The optimization of agrotechnical measures and the results obtained in variants where plowing was carried out at both depths were different. In variants where plowing was carried out at the same depth, yield, protein output, oil output, and the weight of 1000 seeds were higher in variants irrigated with drip irrigation and with a fertilizer norm of N100P80K50 kg per hectare. However, in variants plowed at a depth of 20-25 cm, where drip irrigation and a fertilizer norm of N100P80K50 kg per hectare were applied, the indicators were higher.

According to the State Statistics Committee, 17,181 ha of legumes were planted in our country in 2019, 35,947 tons of products were produced, and the average yield of legumes was 20.9 c/ha. In the Ganja-Gazakh region, 605 ha of land produced 1,076 tons of products, with an average yield of 17.7 c/ha, and in the Samukh district, 21 ha of land produced 54 tons of products, with an average yield of 25.6 c/ha.

The vegetation period of early-maturing soybean varieties is 100 days. When sowing is carried out on May 5-10, it is possible to obtain a high yield. During this period, the weather conditions are favorable for the

development of the plant. Therefore, the most important technological cultivations are the application of fertilizers and herbicides.

In recent years, early-maturing soybean varieties have been developed by Russian breeders. These varieties provide high yields in both spring and second sowings. For example, the SK AGRA variety is early-maturing, with a vegetation period of 104 days. An effective temperature of 1900-21000 C is considered favorable for the development of the variety. It fully matures in the second and third decades of August. The potential yield of the variety is 3.8 t/ha, and in repeated sowings, it is 2.7 t/ha. The grain contains 41-42% protein and 22-24% oil.

In addition to seed production, high-energy feed is prepared from the above-ground mass of soybeans. Such feeds prepared from the green mass of soybeans contain 21-22 feed units and 3.5-4.2 kg of digestible protein.

As seen from the table, in the variant plowed at a depth of 15-20 cm, under pivot irrigation with a fertilizer norm of N80P60K40 per hectare, the yield was 28.4 c/ha; in the variant plowed at a depth of 15-20 cm, under pivot irrigation with a fertilizer norm of N100P80K50 per hectare, the yield was 30.5 c/ha; in the variant plowed at a depth of 15-20 cm, under drip irrigation with a fertilizer norm of N80P60K40 per hectare, the yield was 33.6 c/ha; and in the variant plowed at a depth of 15-20 cm, under drip irrigation with a fertilizer norm of N100P80K50 per hectare, the yield was 35.0 c/ha.

In the variant plowed at a depth of 20-25 cm, under pivot irrigation with a fertilizer norm of N80P60K40 per hectare, the yield was 30.8 centners/ha; in the variant plowed at a depth of 20-25 cm, under pivot irrigation with a fertilizer norm of N100P80K50 per hectare, the yield was 32.6 centners/ha; in the variant plowed at a depth of 20-25 cm, under drip irrigation with a fertilizer norm of N80P60K40 per hectare, the yield was 34.2 centners/ha; and in the variant plowed at a depth of 20-25 cm, under drip irrigation with a fertilizer norm of N100P80K50 per hectare, the yield was 36.1 centners/ha.

In the variant plowed at a depth of 15-20 cm, under pivot irrigation with a fertilizer norm of N80P60K40 per hectare, the protein output was 38.4-38.7%; in the variant plowed at a depth of 15-20 cm, under pivot irrigation with a fertilizer norm of N100P80K50 per hectare, it was 38.9-40.1%; in the variant plowed at a depth of 15-20 cm, under drip irrigation with a fertilizer norm of N80P60K40 per hectare, it was 40.6-43.1%; and in the variant plowed at a depth of 15-20 cm, under drip irrigation with a fertilizer norm of N100P80K50 per hectare, it was 42.6-43%.

In the variant plowed at a depth of 20-25 cm, under pivot irrigation with a fertilizer norm of N80P60K40 per hectare, the protein output was 39.4-40.2%; in the variant plowed at a depth of 20-25 cm, under pivot irrigation with a fertilizer norm of N100P80K50 per hectare, it was 41.3-41.9%; in the variant plowed at a depth of 20-25 cm, under drip irrigation with a fertilizer norm of N80P60K40 per hectare, it was 42.9-43.7%; and in the variant plowed at a depth of 20-25 cm, under drip

irrigation with a fertilizer norm of N100P80K50 per hectare, it was 43.8-43.9%.

In the variant plowed at a depth of 15-20 cm, under pivot irrigation with a fertilizer norm of N80P60K40 per hectare, the oil output was 17.6-18.5%; in the variant plowed at a depth of 15-20 cm, under pivot irrigation with a fertilizer norm of N100P80K50 per hectare, it was 18.8-20.1%; in the variant plowed at a depth of 15-20 cm, under drip irrigation with a fertilizer norm of N80P60K40 per hectare, it was 20.7-21.2%; and in the variant plowed at a depth of 15-20 cm, under drip irrigation with a fertilizer norm of N100P80K50 per hectare, it was 21.3-21.9%.

In the variant plowed at a depth of 20-25 cm, under pivot irrigation with a fertilizer norm of N80P60K40 per hectare, the oil output was 19.6-20.9%; in the variant plowed at a depth of 20-25 cm, under pivot irrigation with a fertilizer norm of N100P80K50 per hectare, it was 21.2-21.8%; in the variant plowed at a depth of 20-25 cm, under drip irrigation with a fertilizer norm of N80P60K40 per hectare, it was 22.0-22.6%; and in the variant plowed at a depth of 20-25 cm, under drip irrigation with a fertilizer norm of N100P80K50 per hectare, it was 22.9-23.5%.

In the variant plowed at a depth of 15-20 cm, under pivot irrigation with a fertilizer norm of N80P60K40 per hectare, the weight of 1000 seeds was 133.2-135.1 grams; in the variant plowed at a depth of 15-20 cm,

under pivot irrigation with a fertilizer norm of N100P80K50 per hectare, it was 135.4-136.9 grams; in the variant plowed at a depth of 15-20 cm, under drip irrigation with a fertilizer norm of N80P60K40 per hectare, it was 136.2-137.4 grams; and in the variant plowed at a depth of 15-20 cm, under drip irrigation with a fertilizer norm of N100P80K50 per hectare, it was 138.1-139.7 grams.

In the variant plowed at a depth of 20-25 cm, under pivot irrigation with a fertilizer norm of N80P60K40 per hectare, the weight of 1000 seeds was 135.6-137.8 grams; in the variant plowed at a depth of 20-25 cm, under pivot irrigation with a fertilizer norm of N100P80K50 per hectare, it was 137.4-138.9 grams; in the variant plowed at a depth of 20-25 cm, under drip irrigation with a fertilizer norm of N80P60K40 per hectare, it was 138.1-139.7 grams; and in the variant plowed at a depth of 20-25 cm, under drip irrigation with a fertilizer norm of N100P80K50 per hectare, it was 140.1-142.6 grams.

Thus, mineral fertilizers have a significant impact on the structural indicators of soybeans in irrigated gray-brown (chestnut) soils. In all cases, in variants irrigated with drip irrigation and a fertilizer norm of N100P80K50 per hectare, the yield was 5-8 centners/ha higher, protein output was 3-5% higher, oil output was 4-6% higher, and the weight of 1000 seeds was 5-10 grams higher.

Table 3.5.

Variants and Their Impact on the Structural Indicators of the Soybean Variety Sigalia

Plowing Depth (cm)	Irrigation Methods	Fertilizer Norms (kg/ha)	Yield (centners/ha)	Protein Output (%)	Oil Output (%)	Mass of 1000 Seeds (g)
15-20 cm	Pivot Irrigation	N80P60K40	28.4	38.4-38.7	17.6-18.5	133.2-135.1
		N100P80K50	30.5	38.9-40.1	18.8-20.1	135.4-136.9
	Drip Irrigation	N80P60K40	33.6	40.6-42.3	20.7-21.2	136.2-137.4
		N100P80K50	35.0	42.6-43.2	21.3-21.9	138.1-139.7
20-25 cm	Pivot Irrigation	N80P60K40	30.8	39.4-40.2	19.6-20.9	135.6-137.8
		N100P80K50	32.6	41.3-41.9	21.2-21.8	137.4-138.9
	Drip Irrigation	N80P60K40	34.2	42.9-43.7	22.0-22.6	138.1-139.7
		N100P80K50	36.1	43.8-43.9	22.9-23.5	140.1-142.6

Conclusion

The growing season of fast-maturing soybean varieties is 100 days. High yields can be achieved when sowing takes place between May 5-10, during which weather conditions are favorable for plant development. Among the most important technological treatments are the application of fertilizers and herbicides. On irrigated grey-brown (chestnut) soils, mineral fertilizers significantly impact the structural indicators of soybeans. In all cases, the variants irrigated with drip irrigation and applying N100P80K50 fertilizer per hectare showed a yield increase of 5-8 centners/ha, protein content increase of 3-5%, oil content increase of 4-6%, and a 1000-seed weight increase of 5-10 grams.

Mineral fertilizers significantly impact the structural indicators of soybeans on irrigated grey-brown (chestnut) soils. Depending on the forms of agrotechnical measures applied in the research area, in all cases, the variants with drip irrigation and N100P80K50 fertilizer application per hectare showed a yield increase of 5-8 centners/ha, protein content increase of 3-5%, oil content increase of 4-6%, and a 1000-seed weight increase of 5-10 grams.

References

- Əliyev İ.H. "Azərbaycan Respublikası regionlarının 2019–2023-cü illərdə sosial-iqtisadi inkişafı Dövlət Proqramı" Bakı şəhəri, 29 yanvar 2019-cu il.

2. Габайдуллина Р.С., Дорохина О.А. Анализ влияния соевых продуктов на жизнедеятельность лабораторных мышей // Альманах молодой науки. – 2015. – № 1. – С. 18-20.
3. Гуреева Е.В., Фомина Т.А. Соя-источник растительного белка // М.: Аграрная наука, 2017, №11-12, с.20-21.
4. Зайцев В.Н. Влияние климатических факторов на продуктивность сои // Новые сорта сельскохозяйственных культур составная часть инновационных технологий в растениеводстве: Сб. научных материалов.
5. Лукомец В.М., Пенчуков В.М., Тильба В.А., Зайцев Н.И., Шабалдас О.Г., Бушнев А.С. Совершенствование технологии возделывания сои // Вестник АПК Ставрополя. – 2015, № 2 (72), с. 88–95.
6. Новиков В.М. Продуктивность гороха и сои в зависимости от основной обработки почвы и минеральных удобрений // Зернобобовые и крупяные культуры, 2013, № 2 (6), с. 106–112.
7. Смирнов С.Г., Нафиков М.М., Фомин В.Н. Урожайность семян сои в лесостепи Поволжья при разных приёмах возделывания // М.: Кормопроизводство, 2014, № 1, с. 17–19.
8. Хамоков Х.А. Продуктивность посевов сои в зависимости от приёмов агротехники на чернозёмах обыкновенных // Известия Оренбургского ГАУ, 2016, № 2 (58), с. 26–28.